

DEFINITIONS

Acute on chronic liver failure was diagnosed based on the EASL-CLIF, as follows: absence of ACLF - (1) no organ failure, (2) single organ failure in patients with a serum creatinine level of <1,5 mg/dL and no hepatic encephalopathy, (3) cerebral failure in patients with a serum creatinine level of <1.5 mg/dL, ACLF grade 1 - (1) single kidney failure, (2) single liver, coagulation, circulatory or lung failure that is associated with a serum creatinine level of 1.5-1.9 mg/dL and/or hepatic encephalopathy grade 1 or grade 2, (3) single brain failure with a serum creatinine level of 1.5-1.9 mg/dL, ACLF grade 2 - two organ failures, ACLF grade 3 - three organ failures or more ¹. The scores predicting mortality of patients with ACLF, considering CLIF-C ACLF Score, age and white cell count has been calculated.

Respiratory failure. In patients without symptoms of respiratory failure we assumed that PaO₂ was 100 mmHg and SaO₂ was 98% unless we had the results of arterial blood gases. In patients requiring oxygen therapy, we assumed that the approximate FiO₂ was as follows: 0.21 for room air, 0.44 for nasal cannula, 0.55 for simple mask, unless specific ventilator settings have been provided.

Encephalopathy. Encephalopathy was diagnosed and classified according to the West Haven scale. In addition, we assumed that patients with elevated levels of ammonia but in which the records did not mention encephalopathy and patients without encephalopathy but receiving lactulose or aspartate ornithine were encephalopathic (minimal neurological disorder; West – Haven hepatic encephalopathy grade 1-2).

Acute liver decompensation was defined by the recent development of ascites, encephalopathy, GI haemorrhage, bacterial infection or any combination of these.

Acute gastrointestinal bleeding was defined as: (1) endoscopically confirmed active variceal or non-variceal bleeding (2) clinical symptoms of acute upper gastrointestinal bleeding

(hematemesis or bloody stools with simultaneous hemodynamic instability – systolic blood pressure below 100 mmHg, heart rate above 100/min) and endoscopic features of recent variceal hemorrhage (e.g., white nipple on the varix), or non-variceal hemorrhage (peptic or esophageal ulcer with stigmata of recent hemorrhage - active spurting, non-bleeding visible vessel, active oozing, adherent clot, Mallory – Weiss tear) (3) medium or large esophageal or gastric varices with red markings or peptic/esophageal ulcer with flat pigmented spot or clean base and clinical symptoms of acute upper gastrointestinal bleeding in patient with no other endoscopically identified potential source of bleeding within upper gastrointestinal tract. All patients with bleeding were treated according to the protocol adopted in our hospital. In brief, after the assessment of hemodynamic status and hemoglobin concentration, resuscitation of blood volume was initiated. We apply a restrictive blood transfusion strategy with a goal of 7-9 g/dL of Hb concentration, and target concentrations above 9 g/dL in selected patients considering comorbidities, age, and hemodynamic status. All patients underwent upper endoscopy within 24 hours of admission to the hospital. Patients with confirmed stigmata of recent non-variceal bleeding (active bleeding, non-bleeding visible vessel, adherent clot) received endoscopic combination therapy (at least two of the following techniques: clipping, bipolar electrocoagulation, injection therapy), and in case variceal bleeding endoscopic band ligation (EBL) or cyanoacrylate injection was used. Patients after endoscopic treatment received intravenous PPI (a bolus followed by continuous infusion) for non-variceal bleeding or intravenous somatostatin (a bolus followed by continuous infusion) or terlipressin (intravenous boluses) for variceal bleeding. Recurrent bleeding after endoscopic treatment was treated with second endoscopic therapy. If this therapy was ineffective, surgical treatment or interventional radiology was undertaken. Endoscopic procedures were performed under general anesthesia (propofol, fentanyl, midazolam) with endotracheal intubation in patients with high risk of aspiration. Most of the procedures were performed at the hospital emergency

department, patients were transferred to the gastroenterology department after successful endoscopic treatment.

5-day treatment failure was defined using Baveno V criteria ².

References:

1. Moreau R, Jalan R, Gines P, et al. Acute-on-chronic liver failure is a distinct syndrome that develops in patients with acute decompensation of cirrhosis. *Gastroenterology*. Jun 2013;144(7):1426-37, 1437.e1-9. doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2013.02.042
2. de Franchis R, Faculty BV. Revising consensus in portal hypertension: report of the Baveno V consensus workshop on methodology of diagnosis and therapy in portal hypertension. *J Hepatol*. Oct 2010;53(4):762-8. doi:10.1016/j.jhep.2010.06.004